

Geography in their classes riddle , poem and from proverbs of use education educational importance

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Abstract: The use of riddles, poems and proverbs in geography lessons has a great educational value. Poem and proverbs to the students topics in learning motivation will give and their understand increases . And this of students to lessons interest raises and to them knowledge receiver interest and talent creates Geography in their classes poem and proverbs with in education of use important role about Poem and proverbs , geography topics in learning to the students motivation will give and their understand more increases . And this of students to lessons interest raises and to them knowledge receiver interest and talent creates In this way education methodology of students geography science more interesting to the relationship have to be help to give can

Key words : interactive methods , methodology , innovative methods , poetry and proverbs ,

Introduction : Geography in their classes riddle , poem and from proverbs of use education educational importance very big Poem and proverbs to students geography topics in learning instruction by doing help will give and them appropriation through studied to remember knowledge help will give . These are students for of classes interesting and to the goal according to to be provides . Poem and from proverbs use , geography topics to study inspiration give , students more interesting to do take will come and their understanding strengthens Such education methods educational important have because they are students knowledge good learned and them strengthening through interesting environment in creating important role plays From this except , poem and proverbs through geography in their classes riddle to education development for human feeling also expands the places . This methods through students mind travel to the feeling block , geography from the topics more enjoyable ones they get In this educational the process continues because students their joys developed and new knowledge ease with those who are learning is considered

Main Part : Proverb is one of the genres of folk oral creativity with compact form but deep content, which was created on the basis of centuries-old life observations, socio-economic, political and cultural experiences of the people . According to their socio-ideological functions, proverbs mainly represent the worldview of the general public, and in some cases, of some social classes or groups. For this reason, the thematic scope of proverbs is very wide, and this scope cannot be limited to the scope of material life reality; there is no area of social existence that is not reflected in proverbs.

Proverbs have a special educational value due to the fact that they arise on the basis of many centuries of life experiences. Because every proverb is tested several times by people's life experiences and living conditions over many years. As a result, proverbs undergo very few changes both in form and content, and have the characteristic of long survival. The spread of each proverb among the people is as slow as its creation. Because the geographical environment that receives a particular proverb makes it its property only after re-testing it in its own conditions. According to Russian folklorist VP Anikin, "What is not in the experience of the people cannot be in the proverb." And people's experience gradually accumulates and enriches over the centuries. Therefore, here the wealth of proverbs that arise in connection with these experiences will also be enriched. In general, proverbs reflect any cause-and-effect relationships in the life of the people in terms of space and time, because it is an invaluable community of people's wise men born as a fist.

Proverbs are a necessary tool for our speech to express our thoughts clearly and figuratively. That is why VGBelinsky considered folk proverbs and sayings to be "the essence of poetry".

As in the proverbs of other nations, Uzbek folk proverbs fully express the way of life, spiritual image, worldview, attitude to work, people, life, and nature of the Uzbek people. That's why the great Russian writer LNT Tolstoy wrote about how close proverbs are to the life and spiritual world of the people: "In every proverb I see the image of the people who created this proverb."

So, from ancient times until now, many instructive statements have been made about the great ethical and aesthetic importance of folk proverbs in the life of mankind, and all of them emphasize that proverbs are an extraordinary phenomenon in the history of social thought.

The term proverb is derived from the Arabic word "qavlun" (to say, to speak), and in the Uzbek language it has become the term of one of the aphoristic genres, which is an example of folk wisdom and expresses the meaning of a well-said word, sentence or phrase. means

The proverb as an independent folklore genre has a number of unique features, which sharply distinguish it from other aphoristic genres, in particular, material.

The proverb reflects all existing areas of people's life with all their contradictions. The wide range of content in proverbs allows for a surprising amount of changes in the nature of each proverb, especially in its semantic nature, over time. Such a situation opens the way for the use of some proverbs within several topics, and this feature gives life to each proverb.

Conclusion The use of riddles, poems and proverbs in geography lessons has a high educational value. Poems and articles written in this language help students to learn geography topics in an interesting and informative way. These types of texts help students to gain a deeper understanding of the concepts learned in classes and increase their interest in them.

Through poems and articles, students will be able to understand geography topics through real-world examples. Such texts basically humanity history, natural substances, economy and another geography topics about will be

Education in the process poem and from the articles use of students language knowledge develop and discuss abilities to strengthen help to give can Of this as a result of students geography from science usage qualities more rising, their theoretical knowledge practical in life apply opportunity appear will be

Also a poem and from the articles use education in the process to students literature to develop knowledge can And this them to humanity about autonomous poem and proverbs to understand help giving their culture and to literature according to knowledge more by expanding to go means

Suggestions :

1. Geography in their classes poem and from the articles wide let it be used .
2. Students relationship enhancer poems let me know
3. In class many p letter from copies let it be used .
4. Educational method to materials important importance to give need
5. To students interesting geography on the subject poems pronunciation don't let them please ask can

6. Poem and proverbs archive collect

Used books

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